

Thermal characterization

To verify the stability of the environmental chamber before behavioral testing, the thermal control subsystem was characterized through setpoint-transition tests. When a target temperature of 35 °C was programmed, the chamber exhibited the expected response of a PID-regulated system, consisting of an initial transient rise, a moderate overshoot, and subsequent convergence toward a stable stationary regime.

Accordingly, the programmed chamber temperature and the independently measured environmental chamber air temperature were considered the primary thermal reference variables throughout the experiments, whereas thermal-camera measurements were treated only as approximate surface-temperature estimates.

The integrated platform operated reliably under the programmed environmental conditions and provided stable, synchronized acquisition of locomotor and environmental signals throughout the experimental sessions. Thermal characterization of the chamber showed that the PID-controlled system reached the programmed setpoint with a settling time of approximately 2–3 min, a moderate transient overshoot, and a steady-state error close to ± 0.25 °C, indicating sufficient stability for reproducible behavioral testing.

In parallel, the illumination subsystem generated clearly differentiated experimental light conditions while maintaining effective isolation from ambient light under the no-light configuration. These results confirmed that the platform was suitable for both thermal experiments and controlled illumination assays, and that subsequent behavioral differences could be interpreted against a stable and well-characterized environmental background.